

After the Terror Attacks in Hanau: Are German Postmigrants' Demands for Linguistic Changes in the Public Debate finally being Heard?

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Either I am living in a Twitter bubble, or something really has changed in Germany's public debate after the February 19 right-wing terror events in Hanau. Listening to the news in different media outlets, I realize that my impression is right. Mainstream media's coverage of the shootings in Hanau[i], leaving nine people dead is linguistically more self-reflective than usually. It seems like most journalists acknowledge what descendants of immigrants have been demanding for a long time: That racism and right-wing extremism are an inescapable reality in Germany. And that what has been designated as *Ausländerfeindlichkeit* (hostility against foreigners) and *Fremdenfeindlichkeit* (Xenophobia) needs to be acknowledged discursively and linguistically for what it is: racism.

Much faster than usually public television designates the terror attacks in Hanau as racially motivated, only initially representing the deed as *fremdenfeindlich* (xenophobic).[ii] Mainstream media's journalists seem to understand that representing the attacks as xenophobic acts actually supports the perpetrator's perspective since it presupposes that the designated don't belong to German society. Born and raised in Germany, the victims in Hanau and their families are by no means foreign or alien. They belong just as much to German society as any ethnic German person.

In addition, all political parties in the German parliament (*Bundestag*) – except the right-wing populist AfD – agree for the first time that Germany has a problem with racism and right-wing extremism. Responding to experts' and migrant associations' demands in the aftermath of the attack, the Federal Cabinet has set up a committee to fight right-wing extremism and racism.[iii] Ferda Ataman, chairwoman and spokeswoman of the postmigrant network 'New German Media Makers' (*Neue Deutsche Medienmacher*) and of the 'New German Organizations' (*Neue Deutsche Organisationen*) states that this acknowledgement of racism and right-wing extremism by political parties is remarkable because to this day:

Published: April 7, 2020, 11:24 a.m.

Edited: April 7, 2020, 11:39 a.m.

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“attacks by right-wing extremists were all too often reflexively classified as isolated acts, committed by people who have drifted so far to the right-wing that they are no longer in touch with society. Deeds were all too often explained with mental disorders or ‘humiliation’. Being mentally ill and being a Nazi - for years this was obviously mutually exclusive.”[iv]

Too good to be true? On March 27, some statements of a not yet completed final report of the attack by the Federal Criminal Police Office (*Bundeskriminalamt – BKA*) are leaked. According to the report, the deed was racist, but the culprit allegedly aimed for attention for his conspiracy theories instead of choosing his victims in line with right-wing extremist ideology.[v] Three days later on March 31, the president of the *BKA* reacts in a Tweet stating that an “alleged final report of the BKA does not exist” and that the institution assesses the deed as right-wing-extremist.[vi] Meanwhile, the popular tabloid newspaper *BILD* has published an article with the headline “No Racist Motive in Hanau Murders”.

What is the problem here? Volkan Açar rightfully concludes that differentiating between perpetrator and deed follows a logic of “right-wing extremist motivated murders by a non-right-wing extremist perpetrator”.[vii] However, as Ferda Ataman points out, what counts in a criminal offense is the deed. For the victims of racism and racist violence, it does not matter if the perpetrator acts due to tactical reasons or if s/he is motivated by a racist ideology.[viii]

What has happened before when public debates shifted to the perpetrator’s background was a distraction from what should be foregrounded: Those who are targeted, the murder victims and their relatives.

The events in Hanau need to be contextualized in the history of racially motivated violence with casualties: the planned attack on a Synagogue last year in Halle, the attack on the CDU politician Walter Lübcke in the same year, the attack in Munich’s Olympia shopping center in 2016, or the ten murders by the terrorist organization Nation Socialist Underground (NSU) between 2000 and 2007, to only name the recent related events. Repeatedly, public authorities and the media have classified racially motivated offenders as single perpetrators with psychological issues. Matthias Quent, who researches about right-wing extremism at the Institute of Democracy and Civil Society in Jena underlines that such assessments have disregarded that acting alone may present part of a strategy and radicalization does not take place out of the blue. [ix] Offenders’ social networks are not less relevant or real if located in Social Media. In addition, the political climate counts as well. Not only do we have a right-wing populist party in German parliament. Racist groups are on the rise in Germany, presenting their ideologies in different platforms[x].

While authorities of the federal republic register only 94 racially motivated casualties, the Amadeu Antonio Foundation[xi] registers 208 victims since Germany’s reunification.[xii] This variation in numbers can be related to the state authorities’ unwillingness in acknowledging racially motivated violence.

A discussion of about the perpetrator’s motives initiated by the media and BKA is evocative of institutional malfunctioning in the investigation of racially-motivated crimes. In defining what racism is, politicians, state institutions and media representatives should listen to what the ones who experience it have to say. This is also why prioritizing the victims’ perspective is crucial. The discussion about the perpetrator needs to be contextualized with German state authorities’ blindness and failure in solving cases of racially-motivated violence, for example, the NSU murders or the murders in the Olympia shopping center[xiii]. Beyond the terrifying deeds of the NSU, it is scandalous how for years neither police nor the German Intelligence suspected a racist motive behind the deeds. Hundreds of officers investigated for years in the wrong direction, contributing to further suffering

by “wrongly and knowingly accusing the murder victims”[xiv]. Attempts by the accessory prosecution to negotiate the racist dimension of the NSU complex and to introduce the perspectives of the victims’ families into the trial were prevented, excluding their knowledge. *Ausländerfeindlichkeit and Fremdenfeindlichkeit*, instead of racism, were used throughout the trial.[xv]

Against this backdrop, it hardly comes as a surprise that the rap artist Azzi Memo has launched a song on April 3, 2020, against right-wing extremism and racism together with 17 other rappers[xvi] – all of them with migration background. Azzi Memo grew up in the city of Hanau, and he has lost a relative and a friend in the terror attacks. Referring to the first line of the German national anthem, Azzi Memo rhymes:

"Einigkeit, Recht und Freiheit, alles was wir wollten in diesem Land. In Frieden miteinander leben, uns die Hände geben. Blumen anstatt Waffen. Menschen bezahlen mit dem Leben aufgrund ihrer Herkunft, ich kann es nicht fassen/ Im Jahre 2020 ist Rechtsextremismus noch immer 'ne Plage. Limburg, Fulda, Kassel, Hanau oder Halle. Dass die AfD im Bundestag sitzt, ist eine Schande." [xvii]

“Unity, justice and freedom. Everything we wanted, here in this country, to live together in peace, reach out to join hands, flowers instead of weapons. People pay with their lives because of their origins, I can't believe it. In the year 2020 right-wing extremism is still a plague. Limburg, Fulda, Kassel, Hanau or Halle. It's a disgrace that the AfD is in the parliament.”

Beyond the horrors of the attack, it is sad that the understanding of belonging to society in Germany still appears to be tied to an ideal connecting membership to ethnicity. Otherwise, all the quoted members of our society with immigrant relatives would not be forced into a position in which they need to explain their membership to German society. Otherwise, it would self-evident that designations like *ausländerfeindlich* and *fremdenfeindlich* carry othering meanings denying membership. And it would not be the ones targeted by racism explaining that the discussion about racist violence needs to prioritize the deeds of violence and the ones harmed. Then again, it seems like some are finally ready to listen.

[i] See latest blog entries by Lalla Amina Drhimeur: <https://bpy.bilgi.edu.tr/en/blog/racially-motivated-mass-shooting-hanau-germany/>; <https://bpy.bilgi.edu.tr/en/blog/germany-confronted-increasing-strength-far-right-g/>

[ii] A spokesperson of the postmigrant network New German Media Makers (*Neue Deutsche Medienmacher*) has praised the coverage of the attack in Hanau: Klein, I. and Vassiliou-Enz, K. (2020) ‘Berichterstattung über Hanau: „Es geht um Präzision im Journalismus“’, Deutschlandfunk, 24 February. Available at: https://www.deutschlandfunk.de/berichterstattung-ueber-hanau-es-geht-um-praezision-im.2907.de.html?dram:article_id=470976.

[iii] Als/dpa/AFP (2020) ‘Kabinett beschließt Ausschuss gegen Rechtsextremismus’, SPIEGEL, 18 March. Available at: <https://www.spiegel.de/politik/deutschland/anschlag-in-hanau-kabinett-beschliesst-ausschuss-gegen-rechtsextremismus-a-2e67ba24-1437-4b3d-865d-d10efe38bf51>.

[iv] Ataman, F. (2020) ‘BKA-Bericht zu Hanau-Anschlag: Es zählt die Tat, nicht das Motiv’, SPIEGEL, 29 March. Available at: <https://www.spiegel.de/panorama/bka-bericht-zu-hanau-anschlag-es-zaehlt-die-tat-nicht-das-motiv-a-1cf09e9e-8f75-4958-9685-c203aff1eb6a>.

[v] Flade, F. and Mascolo, G. (2020a) 'Anschlag in Hanau: Gefährliche Botschaften', Süddeutsche Zeitung, 28 March. Available at: <https://www.sueddeutsche.de/politik/anschlag-hanau-rechtsextremismus-abschlussbericht-bka-1.4859441>. Flade, F. and Mascolo, G. (2020b) Anschlag von Hanau: Rechte Tat, aber kein rechter Täter?, Tagesschau.de. Available at: <https://www.tagesschau.de/investigativ/ndr-wdr/hanau-taeter-bka-101.html> (Accessed: 4 April 2020).

[vi] BKA (2020) Bundeskriminalamt @bka #BKA-Präsident Holger Münch zur aktuellen Medienberichterstattung im Zusammenhang mit #Hanau, Twitter. Available at: <https://twitter.com/bka/status/1244938778374025218> (Accessed: 4 April 2020).

[vii] Açar, V. (2020) 'Bewertung von Hanau: Deutsches Oxymoron', taz, 1 April.

[viii] Ataman, F. (2020) 'BKA-Bericht zu Hanau-Anschlag: Es zählt die Tat, nicht das Motiv', SPIEGEL, 29 March. Available at: <https://www.spiegel.de/panorama/bka-bericht-zu-hanau-anschlag-es-zaehlt-die-tat-nicht-das-motiv-a-1cf09e9e-8f75-4958-9685-c203aff1eb6a>.

[ix] Maxwill, P. (2019) 'Antisemitischer Anschlag in Halle: Der Einzeltäter, der nicht allein war', SPIEGEL, 10 October. Available at: <https://www.spiegel.de/panorama/justiz/halle-saale-anschlag-auf-synagoge-einzeltaeter-sind-nicht-allein-a-1290818.html> (Accessed: 6 April 2020). Deutschlandfunk (2020) Nach Anschlag in Hanau Trauer und Wut prägen das Gedenken, Deutschlandfunk. Available at: https://www.deutschlandfunk.de/nach-anschlag-in-hanau-trauer-und-wut-praegen-das-gedenken.2897.de.html?dram:article_id=470715 (Accessed: 6 April 2020).

[x] See blog entry by Lalla Amina Drhimeur "Germany is confronted with the increasing strength of far-right groups" <https://bpy.bilgi.edu.tr/en/blog/germany-confronted-increasing-strength-far-right-g/>

[xi] Named after a victim of racially motivated violence, the foundation dedicates its activities to the strengthening of democratic civil society working against racism and extremism.

[xii] Brausam, A. (2020) Todesopfer rechter Gewalt seit 1990, Amadeu Antonio Foundation. Available at: <https://www.amadeu-antonio-stiftung.de/rassismus/todesopfer-rechter-gewalt/> (Accessed: 6 April 2020).

[xiii] Kampf, L. (2020) Attentat in München 2016 Wie politisch motiviert war der Amoklauf?, Tagesschau.de.

[xiv] p. 843: Bundestag, D. (2013) Beschlussempfehlung und Bericht des 2. Untersuchungsausschusses nach Artikel 44 des Grundgesetzes. Available at: <http://dipbt.bundestag.de/dip21/btd/17/146/1714600.pdf>.

[xv] p. 50: Bach, N. (2017) Institutioneller Rassismus im NSU-Prozess Eine Dispositivanalyse. 28. Available at: <https://www.polsoz.fu-berlin.de/polwiss/forschung/systeme/emprosoz/team/ehemalige/publikationen/schriften/arbeitshefte/bach--institutioneller-rassismus-im-nsu-prozess-ahosz28.pdf>.

[xvi] Hessenschau.de (2020) Charity-Aktion von Azzi Memo und anderen 'Der größte Deutschrap-Song ever' zu Ehren der Opfer von Hanau, Hessenschau.de. Available at: <https://www.hessenschau.de/kultur/azzi-memo-und-andere-der-groesste-deutschrap-song-ever-zu-ehren-der-opfer-von-hanau,hanau-azzi-memo-rap-charity-100.html> (Accessed: 4 April 2020). The income generated by the track will be donated to civil society organizations' initiative supporting the families and the survivors of the terror attack: <https://www.amadeu-antonio-stiftung.de/hanau/>

[xvii] Memo, A. (2020) Bist du wach? (Benefiz für Hanau) (feat. Nate57, Veysel, Sinan G, Kool Savas, NKS N, Rola, Disarstar, Maestro, Hanybal, Celo & Abdi, Manuellsen, Silla, Credibil, Ali471, Milonair, Mortel, KEZ) · Azzi Memo · Nate57 · Veysel · Sinan G · Kool Savas · NKS N · R, YouTube. Available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fu19AeFuf-I&feature=youtu.be> (Accessed: 4 March 2020). <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fu19AeFuf-I&feature=youtu.be>

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